

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH RESULTS ANALYZING THE MEASUREMENT OF ABSORPTIVE CAPACITY IN COMPANIES IN LATIN AMERICA

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ABSTRACT

The study of Absorptive Capacity (AB) in organizations has been carried out for at least a quarter of a century by national and international researchers. And since the mid-1990s, some research has prioritized measuring a company's absorptive capacity. Therefore, the objective of this research is to carry out comparisons of the results of research in Latin America that use similar definitions and measures for absorptive capacity. For this research, a bibliographic research has already been carried out to understand a little more about the subject, and a systematic review will be carried out and, finally, a comparative content analysis will be carried out to verify studies that present similar instruments for measuring the absorption capacity within each area. of knowledge. The tool used for the research is and will be the Portal de Periódicos da Capes to encompass a comprehensive research, and the Web Of Science and Scielo databases to refine it. This study will contribute significantly to the literature, helping future researchers to use a measurement instrument closer to the study in question, based on an analysis carried out in similar studies that proposed and validated instruments to measure absorptive capacity in Latin American companies. America.

Keywords: Absorptive Capacity. Measurement. Latin America.

INTRODUCTION

Absorptive capacity appears in the literature as one of the most significant constructs in organizational research in recent years (FLATTEN, ENGELEN, ZAHRA, BRETTEL, 2011; LANE, KOKA, PATHAK, 2002; VOLBERDA, FOSS, LYLES, 2010).

For the precursors of the theme Cohen and Levinthal (1990), absorptive capacity (AC) was conceptualized as the process of recognizing the value of external knowledge, interpreting it and applying it in business practice. This concept was introduced by these authors when they argued that when an organization wants to obtain and use knowledge that is not linked to its current knowledge, efforts are necessary to develop this capacity.

In 1890, Alfred Marshall already considered that knowledge is the most important engine of production. Through information, technology and the learning process, knowledge began to become a factor of production, modifying current social, cultural and economic relations. It also affects current market relations, becoming a differentiator in the way of production, providing economic growth.

In 1959, Edith Penrose admitted the firm as a warehouse of training and knowledge, where the experience acquired ends up affecting productive services. The author understands that absorptive capacity is based on existing knowledge that will organize the identification of new opportunities and external knowledge and affect the way in which they will be incorporated and explored internally (PENROSE, 1959).

The environment always undergoes changes and this ends up causing the accumulation of skills through the innovative agent and the firm. Learning over time provides the improvement of technologies and gains in productivity, benefiting its place in the market and preserving the organization's competitiveness (PENROSE, 1959).

In this way, the organization recognizes the importance of external knowledge and needs to determine how to internalize it. This process requires internal absorption structures, as the assimilation process originates from prior internal knowledge of the organization's elements, organizational methods, routines, complementary capabilities and external relationships (COHEN AND LEVINTHAL, 1990).

Based on Cohen and Levinthal's (1990) definition, studies intended to expand the concept (Zahra & George, 2002) with the purpose of broadening the focus on absorptive capacity. It was then that Zahra and George (2002) defined AC as the ability to absorb, assimilate, transform and explore external knowledge, and through this ability external knowledge is explored for profitable purposes in institutions. The concept of absorptive capacity is related to social innovation, the result of a complex process of knowledge codification.

In this way, assimilation activities enable learning recognized and acquired individually to be adjusted to the organizational scope, making it understandable and transferable to other elements of the organization, and in the application phase at the individual level – it comprises the internalization of the new knowledge in everyday work activities (NONAKA, 1994).

External knowledge allows the organization's internal knowledge to be developed, stimulating competitiveness and innovation. In order to boost knowledge resources, employees must be able to learn new knowledge and use it in their task environment (MATUSIK AND HEELEY, 2005).

Because companies with a high degree of absorptive capacity tend to be more effective and explore opportunities more, regardless of their current performance (COHEN AND LEVINTHAL, 1990). Managers need to coordinate activities that produce knowledge with the aim of improving the companies' production process, adding value. (SORDI; AZEVEDO, 2008; NONAKA; TAKEUCHI, 2008; NONAKA; VON KROGH, 2009).

Therefore, it is increasingly necessary to establish management strategies with the purpose of boosting internal knowledge and making employees assist in new information, extracting important data and processing it in a way appropriate to the company's demands (NOWACKI; BACHNIK, 2015).

Given the above, since the mid-90s, some research has prioritized measuring the absorptive capacity of a company, as measuring CA is a method surrounded by doubts, making these measurements quite delicate (VERSIANI *et al.* , 2010, p.7). According to the same authors, two important foundations are highlighted for developing measurement instruments. The first is that through measurement, intervention techniques can be proposed through diagnosis. The second reason is that only through measurement, particularly quantitative measurement, is it possible to make comparisons between organizations, providing a better understanding of realities. In this way, measurement favors results for questions about the most favorable situations for the creation, dissemination and introduction of external knowledge, informing the reasons why some companies achieve extraordinary results and others do not (VERSIANI *et al.* , 2010, p.7) .

The most common measure involved evaluating the level of absorptive capacity based on the equation in which the R&D effort made by the company (normally determined by R&D expenditure) is divided by annual sales (COHEN AND LEVINTHAL, 1990; BECKER AND PETERS, 2000 ; ZAHRA AND HAYTON, 2008). Although it is simple to operate such a measure, it does not represent the richness of the construct, as it is unaware of significant precedents, for example, the skills and experiences of employees in the position, the usual language developed within the organization, organizational memory, among others (FLATTEN *et al.* , 2011; LANE, KOKA, PATHAK, 2006; ZAHRA AND GEORGE, 2002).

According to Cassol *et al.* (2016) although research measures AC in companies through quantitative methods, some research presents theoretical and empirical discussions with the purpose of qualitatively analyzing the absorptive capacity. And Lana *et al.* (2018) state that there are reasons why certain statistical techniques are used more than others.

Therefore, this work is justified by the importance of making comparisons between articles that use similar definitions and measurements for absorptive capacity, contributing

significantly to the literature, helping future researchers in the use of a measurement instrument that comes closest to the study. In question, based on an analysis carried out in similar studies that proposed and validated instruments for measuring absorptive capacity in companies in Latin America.

According to the above, the following research problem arises: What are the most used absorptive capacity measurement instruments in each area of knowledge and what are the validation distinctions between similar instruments?

To answer this question, the objectives mentioned below will be used.

Goals

In order to achieve results that meet the research question, general and specific objectives were determined, presented below:

Main goal

Make comparisons of research results from Latin America that use similar definitions and measurements for absorptive capacity.

Specific objectives

The following specific objectives were established to help achieve the purpose of this research:

- a. Describe what Absorptive Capacity is from the perspective of different authors;
- b. Carry out a comparison between variations in the CA definition, establishing points of convergence and divergence, as well as a timeline of their modifications;
- c. Depict the methods used to measure absorptive capacity in companies;
- d. Carry out a comparative analysis of research results that analyze the measurement of absorptive capacity in companies in Latin America, within each area of knowledge.

Marshallian and Penrosian views on knowledge

Marshall did not treat production simply as a combination of capital, labor and natural resources. Because firms, markets and economies comprise organization and knowledge, in addition to traditional factors of production. In this way, knowledge and organization are

instruments of development in both the public and private spheres (Principles of Economics, Book IV, p. 203, 1996).

Marshall noted the need to facilitate the process of circulating and sharing information within firms through their own communication channels or specialized sources, with the aim of causing a true overflow of knowledge (ALVARES, 2019). He created the representative firm, based on the knowledge that markets are populated by firms that are heterogeneous in age and capabilities. This firm with competitive power, capabilities and access to internal economies. And it was only later that a succession of collaborations by other authors ended up replacing the representative firm solution with homogeneous firms occupying the markets in long-run equilibrium. (MOSS, 1984).

For the Marshallian view, more than accumulating capital, the firm accumulates capabilities, knowledge, develops its internal organization, determines and expands its clientele. It is through the ability to introduce new solutions to business problems that the capabilities and knowledge of companies will be developed, so that they can deal with the problems resulting from growth (Principles of Economics, Book IV, p. 348, 356, 1996) .

This author sees increasing income as essential in industrial activity. Because these increasing returns appear both at the level of the firm and in the grouping of firms, whether in markets, regions or national economies. And it is in this circumstance that Marshall proposes the concepts of internal economies and external economies. Internal economies represent changes in performance that comprise the increase in the proportion of firms. The performance of firms benefits from their size because of the advantages of purchasing a greater quantity of inputs at more advantageous prices, access to methods of marketing and advertising blocked to smaller businesses, the possibility of using specialized machinery, labor and management, in the ability to cover the expenses and risk of research activity (Principles of Economics, Book IV, p. 362, 363, 303-315, 1996).

Marshall proposed that as production increases, costs can be reduced due to external economies, which are economies of agglomeration of different businesses in a region, so that the qualifications of workers, the secrets of production and specialized services are shared. by local manufacturers who can improve and adapt their equipment to a narrow range of operations, with subdivision of a broad demand between different types of products in the same category (Principles of Economics, Book IV, p.317-325, 1996).

Although growth based on external economies symbolizes a possibility for growth based on internal economies, Marshall advocates that a space for the growth of small companies is reformulated by the development of large ones, as companies of different proportions can

complement each other, rather than dispute (Principles of Economics, Book IV, p. 328-331, 1996).

In his book Principles of Economics, Marshall brings the lesson of young trees in the forest that try to overtake the shadow of their old competitors. Many end up exhausting themselves along the way, and some resist and become stronger every year, getting more air and more light as they grow and, finally, rise above their competitors and always want to rise higher than the others and become always more robust as they rise. However, this does not happen, as the tree that lasts longer in full robustness and reaches a larger size than the others, sooner or later, will have its age manifested. And even those taller ones that have more access to light and air will gradually lose their energy, giving way to new trees, which have youth in their favor (Principles of Economics, Book IV, p. 360, 1996).

And the author also points out that,

“...the same thing that happens with the growth of trees, happened with the growth of businesses as a general rule before the great recent development of large joint-stock companies, which often stagnate, but do not die easily. Currently, this rule is far from being general, but it still operates in many branches of industry and commerce. Nature still acts upon individual businesses, limiting the duration of the lives of their founders and further reducing the part of their lives during which the full vigor of the faculties is maintained. Thus, after some time, the management of the company falls into the hands of people with less energy and creative spirit, if not with less active interest in its prosperity. If it becomes a joint-stock company, it can retain the advantages of the division of labor, labor and specialized machinery, even expand them through a further increase in capital and, under favorable conditions, obtain a permanent and prominent position in its branch of production. But it is likely to have lost so much of its elasticity and progressive momentum that the advantages no longer remain exclusively on its side in competition with younger and smaller rivals” (Principles of Economics, Book IV, p. 361, 1996).

As growth involves time, larger and older firms, managed by heirs not chosen by the market to represent their founder, and employing old solutions to business problems, will tend to decline, resulting in new firms created by entrepreneurs who have new solutions to the same problems. In this way, monopolization should not occur (Principles of Economics, Book IV, p. 267-282, 1996).

The proposition of a capitalist business environment in constant transformation means that firms that do not perform correctly in innovative activities are destined to decline. This pressure on possible candidates for inefficient monopolists is also characterized by the Marshallian proposition that the potential competition carried out by firms that can be attracted by high prices limits the power of firms that, in the theoretical understanding of traditional

competition, would be considered as having high power. of monopoly (*Industry and Trade* , p.396, 1920).

There is Marshall's influence on Edith Penrose. Marshall's framing of Penrose occurs in the firm's cumulative approach, as the author returned to studies that considered it dynamic. According to Foss (1998), Penrose perfected and radicalized the idea of the firm introduced by Marshall by considering that companies do not house knowledge, but process and develop it.

“This alternative, developed in an original way, is compatible with the discussion about the firm elaborated by Marshall. The two approaches are complementary, have points in common and are perfectly integrable” (KERSTENETZKY, 2000, p. 36)

The contribution that Edith Penrose left was differentiating growth from improving business knowledge about the management and use of resources. She corroborates her thinking by deducing that new knowledge obtained determines the speed of business growth. (ALVARES, 2019).

For Penrose (1995), the firm should be considered an institution that develops by accumulating resources and experiences with a strong dependence on the environment in which it operates. In this way, the firm's growth is a consequence of the unique capabilities and accumulated resources that determine limits to the firm's expansion, within an economic environment that is far from its direct control.

Penrose's theory of firm growth is important because it considers the role of the firm's internal resources to be essential. Because the company will no longer be considered from a neoclassical point of view, where the firm is a “black box” making decisions only about prices and quantities with the sole purpose of increasing profits. But the firms will be considered active and able to influence the market, having financial and investment conduct. In this way, Penrose (1995, p. 7) characterized the company as an administrative unit with boundaries, analyzing firms limited in their growth, caused by the boundaries of teamwork.

According to Edith Penrose (1959), a company's growth occurs through the ability to learn and reorganize its resources, including its management capacity that allows it to expand services to generate growth opportunities. A key factor in Penrose's theory is that a company's capacity for growth is formed by its internal resources and its ability to create dynamic capabilities. The ability to acquire, assimilate and create knowledge from all external and internal sources is a fundamental aspect that establishes the survival and growth of a company.

Knowledge reaches people in two different ways. A species can be formally taught, learned from other people or from written texts, and can, if necessary, be formally expressed and transmitted to third parties. The other kind also

results from learning, but from learning in the form of personal experience. The first modality is what we can call “objective” knowledge. [...] Experience produces a growing knowledge of reality and contributes to “objective” knowledge to the extent that its results can be transmitted to third parties. But the experience itself can never be transmitted. It produces changes – often subtle changes – in individuals, and cannot be separated from them. Increasing knowledge presents itself in two ways: in the form of acquired knowledge and as changes in the ability to use knowledge. There are no rigid distinctions between these forms, since, to a considerable extent, the ability to use old knowledge depends on the acquisition of new ones. (PENROSE, 1959/2006, p. 100-101).

In Penrosian theory, growth is seen as an evolutionary process and based on the cumulative growth of knowledge. Through this accumulation of knowledge, firms will make better use of available internal resources, which will allow them to take advantage of opportunities that would not previously have been possible to achieve. Thus, the limits to the firm's growth are momentary, expanding over time, through the creation of new resources.

In relation to the external environment, during most of Penrose's (1995) work, it was seen as an image of opportunities and barriers in the entrepreneur's mind. In this way, the firm differentiates itself from the market, while its economic activities take place within an administrative organization. Therefore, the larger the firm, the less the intervention of market forces in the allocation of productive resources for different uses and the greater the environment for adequate planning of economic activity.

For Penrose (1995), there are three classes of explanations for the existence of limits to the firm's growth, being: (i) managerial capacity; (ii) factor and product market; and (iii) uncertainty and risk. Managerial capacity deals with conditions within the firm, the second refers to conditions external to the firm, and the third is a combination of internal and external factors. The managerial limit is naturally caused by the physical limits imposed by nature in relation to the number of activities that any person can perform. Therefore, there are natural limits to the expansion of any activity for a certain period of time. These limits are not constant and can be changed as more knowledge or resources are acquired. Learning and acquiring new knowledge can occur in different ways.

In this way, better seeing the available knowledge that can be incorporated by the organization makes firms better deal with the demand for their products (PENROSE, 1959/2006).

Knowledge management

In the mid-1990s, knowledge management developed, in the strategic demarcation of the knowledge-based perspective, in which the firm began to be seen to create and incorporate knowledge (GRANT, 1996). This model emerged based on four movements: the definition of companies' essential competence (HAMEL & PRAHALAD, 1995); the definition of the professional competence profile (LE BOTERF, 2003 ; MCCLELLAND, 1973 ; ZARIFIAN, 2001); the definition of the managerial competence profile (RUAS, 2005 ; SENGE, 1997 ; QUINN, 2004); and from competency management to knowledge management (DAVENPORT & PRUSAK, 1998 ; NONAKA & TAKEUCHI, 1997 ; SVEIBY, 1998 ; VON KROGH *ET AL*, 2001).

Knowledge management (KM) is the process by which added value is created in the company based on the knowledge factor, that is, the coordination and exploitation of the company's knowledge resources, aiming to create benefits and competitive advantages (DRUCKER, 1993) .

Gold, Malhotra and Segars (2001) characterize knowledge management as the ability to manage companies' internal or external knowledge, transforming them into a new idea or technique and using and conserving them.

Therefore, KM is a business strategy, people, technologies and processes to obtain, use, learn, contribute, evaluate, build and maintain knowledge that adds value to generate innovation. If the acquired knowledge does not bring value, it must be discarded to make room in memory for knowledge that is truly relevant to the organizations' essential competence (BUKOWITZ, WILLIAMS, 2002 apud VASCONCELOS, CASTRO, BRITO, 2018).

Efficient knowledge management is extremely important for the success of modern companies, as it identifies the key points of encouragement for a company to achieve business results. Through the knowledge-based perspective, companies are able to achieve two different objectives: the generation of knowledge and the application of knowledge. Furthermore, this perspective identifies that the creation, integration, sharing and application of knowledge benefit companies more than the knowledge itself (CHOU, 2005).

Dasgupta and Gupta (2009) point out that although knowledge is a relevant strategic mechanism, it is not easy to conduct, especially tacit knowledge. Therefore, systems that contribute to this management play an extremely important role in support and coordination (DARROCH, 2005).

Knowledge management for Dasgupta and Gupta (2009) is defined as a system that shapes a collaborative environment, enabling the acquisition and sharing of previous knowledge, creating opportunities to generate new knowledge, and providing tools and approaches necessary to employ them with the purpose of achieving the established goals.

It is through knowledge management that the right knowledge is captured, made available to the user, and used to improve individual or organizational performance (JENNEX, SMOLNIK AND CROASDELL, 2009).

For Miranda, Lee and Lee (2011), knowledge management involves the processes of acquisition, modification and use of knowledge stock, highlighting them as necessary for better performance. And the main objective of knowledge management is to manage knowledge flows (ANDERSÉN, 2012; MASSINGHAM, 2014), which ensures that the flow goes beyond organizational or even geographic boundaries (LIN; WU, 2009).

However, there is no conclusive definition for knowledge management (HUANG, 2014). In this way, several concepts can be identified. Dávila (2016) found several definitions that were sometimes divergent and sometimes partially or completely convergent, expressed in table 1 below:

Table 1 – Definitions of Knowledge Management

Author(s)	Definition
Drucker (1993)	CG is the coordination and exploitation of organizational knowledge resources to create benefit and competitive advantage.
Wiig (1997)	The objective of KM is to maximize the effectiveness and profit that the organization obtains from the constant renewal of its knowledge assets. KM is understanding, focusing on, and managing in a systematic, explicit and deliberate way, the processes that allow you to develop and apply knowledge.
Beijerse (1999, 2000)	KM means achieving organizational objectives, through support, for knowledge workers to improve and apply their data and information interpretation capabilities.
De Long and Fahey (2000)	KM allows improving organizational performance through tools, processes, systems, structures and cultures aimed at improving the creation, sharing and application of knowledge that is critical for decision making.
Harigopal and Satyadas (2001)	KM can be defined as a discipline that provides the strategy, processes and technology to share and maximize information and skills that increase the level of understanding. This improves problem-solving and decision-making capabilities.
Firestone and Mcelroy (2005)	KM is the set of processes that aim to change current patterns of knowledge processing to improve knowledge itself and its results.
Dalkir (2005)	KM is the mix of strategies, tools and techniques, many of them already existing, aimed at improving the efficiency of knowledge and its contribution to organizational objectives.
Gao, Li and Clarke (2008)	KM in a company means managing the activities of knowledge workers, providing these workers with motivation, leadership, support, as well as an appropriate work environment.

Jannex, Smolnik and Croasdell (2009)	KM is about capturing the right knowledge, making it available to the right user, and using that knowledge to improve individual or organizational performance.
North and Kumta (2014)	KM enables individuals, groups, organizations, networks and nations to create, share and apply knowledge systematically to achieve their strategic and operational objectives. KM increases the efficiency and effectiveness of operations by improving competitive quality (innovation) and developing a learning organization.

Source: Dávila (2016, p. 44)

Therefore, based on the analysis carried out in this work, knowledge management is defined as a dynamic effort aligned to a set of strategies, elaborated through methods and supported by practices that aim to enhance the transformation of knowledge into generated value and, consequently, improve organizational performance.

Absorptive capacity

In literature, in 1989, Cohen and Levinthal began to address the topic of absorptive capacity and in 1990 they began a more in-depth study. From 2000 onwards, other studies emerged that strengthened the theories launched by Cohen and Levinthal (1990), and these studies demonstrated their importance in the organizational context. These authors were: Lane, Salk and Lyles (2001), Tsai (2001), Zahra and George (2002), Jansen, Van Den Bosh and Volberda (2005), Lane, Koka and Pathak (2006). And most studies relate absorptive capacity to innovation within organizational processes, through the assimilation and transformation of knowledge capable of encouraging the institution's growth (LANE; KOKA; PATHAK, 2006).

For Cohen and Levinthal (1990), absorptive capacity is the ability of an institution's employees to develop important knowledge bases, identify significant external information, make appropriate decisions and implement appropriate work mechanisms.

The role of absorptive capacity in the assimilation and exploration of knowledge proposes that, both at the individual and organizational levels, existing knowledge enables the assimilation and exploration of new knowledge. In this way, part of this existing knowledge must be deeply linked to the new knowledge so that assimilation is favored (COHEN; LEVINTHAL, 1990). Regarding the other part of this knowledge, it must be diversified, so that the use of new knowledge is effective (COHEN; LEVINTHAL, 1990).

Cohen and Levinthal (1990) determine three dimensions, which are equivalent to three skills that result from the definition of absorptive capacity. The first is the ability to recognize

the value of new external knowledge. To allow the effective and creative use of new knowledge, the factors that provide recognition of the value of external knowledge must have some prior knowledge. Second, the organization must be able to assimilate new external knowledge and define how to internalize it. And third, the organization must be able to commercialize the new external knowledge. Because the more experience companies have in solving similar problems, the simpler it will be for the receiving company to apply the recently assimilated knowledge.

Lane, Salk and Lyles (2001) highlighted the critical role of absorptive capacity in companies' learning and internal performance, and highlighted the different ways in which every component of absorptive capacity influences such results. These authors tested absorptive capacities and discovered relationships with direct and indirect performance (LANE, SALK AND LYLES, 2001).

For Tsai (2001), absorptive capacity is used as a lens to explore the knowledge transfer method. And the work of Tsai (2001) links ACAP to innovation, mainly technological innovation and competitive performance.

The work of Zahra and George (2002) expands the theory developed by Cohen and Levinthal (1990) by considering absorptive capacity as a multi-dimensional construct that encompasses acquisition, assimilation, transformation and exploration of knowledge. Acquisition is the firm's ability to identify and acquire knowledge from external sources (FLATTEN *et al.* , 2011). Assimilation is the routines and processes that provide the firm with the analysis, interpretation and understanding of information obtained from external resources (SZULANSKI, 1996). Transformation indicates the firm's competence in developing routines that allow the connection of existing knowledge and obtained knowledge (ZAHRA; GEORGE, 2002). And exploration is based on routines that enable the firm to improve its knowledge and skills and use them for commercial purposes (LANE; LUBATKIN, 1998; ZAHRA; GEORGE, 2002).

Zahra and George (2002), when expanding the concept of ACAP, kept human capital as an important element for the acquisition and exploitation of knowledge obtained.

The dimensions of absorptive capacity are grouped into two, being the potential absorptive capacity that makes the firm comprehensive in acquiring and assimilating external knowledge, even if this knowledge is not explored (LANE; LUBATKIN, 1998; ZAHRA; GEORGE, 2002) , and the realized absorptive capacity, which is a function of similarities in knowledge and similarities in the cognitive-social context (KIM; HUR; SCHOENHERR, 2015) and corresponds to the transformation of capabilities, which enable the development of new processes and changes in existing processes of the firm (FLATTEN *et al.* , 2011). For Zahra

and George (2002), it is through the realized absorptive capacity that the exploitation of knowledge occurs and the firm's ability to promote the knowledge that has been obtained.

The potential absorptive capacity positively influences the realized absorptive capacity (MONTAZEMI *et al.*, 2012), with restriction of social integration tools, which reduce sharing barriers and increase the competence of knowledge transformation and exploration (ZAHRA; GEORGE, 2002).

The development of companies' acquisition capabilities is influenced by the existing experiences they have. Therefore, exposure to various sources of knowledge does not ensure the development of absorptive capacity, as it is essential that there is complementarity of knowledge with the companies' activities (ZAHRA & GEORGE, 2002).

The study by Jansen, Van Den Bosch and Voberda (2005) recommends that the organization must both determine links with external sources of new knowledge and structure networks to assimilate, transform and explore new external knowledge.

Lane *et al.* (2006) presented a model of exploratory, transformational and exploitative learning. The exploratory dimension encompasses recognizing and understanding the importance of new information. Consecutively, external information is assimilated through a transformation process at the individual and company levels. Finally, exploratory learning enables the application of new knowledge to generate results.

The authors Todorova and Durisin (2007) proposed a partial return to the original absorptive capacity model, reimplanting the recognition of the value of external information and establishing ACAP as a composition of five capabilities. Firstly, the company needs to recognize the value of external knowledge. Secondly, assimilation happens when new information adapts to current cognitive structures. However, when new knowledge cannot be assimilated by current cognitive structures, a process of transformation of existing mental structures must occur (TODOROVA & DURISIN, 2007).

In contrast to the proposal of Zahra and George (2002), Todorova and Durisin (2007) propose three dimensions or abilities of absorptive capacity: (i) recognition, (ii) acquisition and (iii) exploration.

In the same way as Cohen and Levinthal (1990), the authors call the first skill "recognition" of external knowledge. This marks recognition as an important step before acquiring new knowledge, and an essential step.

Vega-Jurado, Gracia-Gutiérrez and Fernández-de-Lucio (2008) and Murovec and Prodan (2009) show the differentiation between industrial absorptive capacity, which is related to the acquisition of knowledge from industrial partners, such as customers, competitors and

suppliers, and scientific capacity related to knowledge originating from universities, technology institutes and private and public research centers.

For Pinto (2015), absorptive capacity is a multidimensional theoretical construct that encompasses a set of routines and organizational processes through which firms generate dynamic organizational capacity. Teixeira *et al.* (2016) characterize that absorptive capacity is based on individual agents committed to problem solving and learning activities associated with the levels of groups and organizations. At the organizational level, to exercise absorptive capacity.

Later for Padilha *et al.* (2016), the company depends on its internal experience, specialized knowledge and appropriate processes, which make it possible to identify and use external knowledge and innovation opportunities.

In short, the author Teixeira (2020) argues in his thesis that,

"... the absorptive capacity and its knowledge base function as "heuristics" for the process of searching and acquiring new external knowledge by the firm, since it is not possible to establish a free price system for such knowledge that is capable to provide all relevant information about them, given their strong intangible content and their indivisibility". (TEIXEIRA, p. 13, 2020).

Still according to the same author, this theme has an elementary bipartite configuration, with the first part facing outside the firm, aimed at identifying and selecting external knowledge, and the second part, facing inside the firm, focused on internalizing, assimilating and commercially exploit external knowledge (TEIXEIRA, p.51, 2020).

In this table 2, it is possible to present an evolution of the fundamental concepts of absorptive capacity.

Table 2 - Evolution of the concept of absorptive capacity

Author	Year	Concept
Cohen and Levinthal	nineteen ninety	It consists of the company's ability to evaluate the value of new external knowledge, assimilate it and apply it for commercial purposes based on 3 dimensions: 1) Recognition of the value of information; 2) The assimilation of knowledge by the company; and 3) Application of knowledge to generate information.
Lane and Lubatkin	1998	Ability of one company to learn from another. CA is determined by the relative characteristics of the two companies.
Zahra and George	2002	It consists of a group of routines and organizational processes through which companies acquire, assimilate, transform and exploit knowledge to produce a dynamic organizational capability.
Todorova and Durisin	2007	Ability to recognize the value of new external knowledge, acquire it, transform it and apply it.
Flatten <i>et al.</i>	2011	Source of competitive advantage through the company's ability to acquire, assimilate, transform and apply external knowledge.

Méndez, Mesa and Alegre	2016	Opening the search for external knowledge that contributes to exploratory and transformative learning processes.
Apriliyanti and Alon	2017	Absorptive capacity reveals research flows in intra-organizational and inter-organizational learning.

Source: Lima e Moreira (2020)

The preliminary evaluation of these definitions was found through a search carried out on the Capes Periodicals portal, covering the 27 studies that were published in the last three years, understanding absorptive capacity as a set of fundamental skills to deal with the tacit part, with the knowledge coming from the transferred environment and the need to transform this imported knowledge.

Measurement of absorptive capacity

Based on the vision of Cohen and Levinthal (1990), as well as Zahra and George (2002), other researchers have sought to clarify the influence of absorptive capacity (AC) on business events. To this end, several authors have created and carried out empirical studies in the search for developing and validating the measurement of absorptive capacity in companies, evaluating the entire process of acquisition, assimilation, transformation and exploration of different types of external knowledge (ZAHRA; GEORGE, 2002 , JANSEN; VAN DEN BOSCH; VOLVERBA, 2005, FOSFURI; TRIBÓ, 2010).

Several authors measure absorptive capacity through a single proxy, such as commitment to Research and Development (R&D) (BEISE; STAHL, 1999; COHEN; LEVINTHAL, 1989, 1990), workforce qualification (BRUNEEL; D' ESTE; SALTER, 2010; GARCIA *et al.* , 2014) and prior citation rate of patents from company j in patents from company i, called cross-citation rate (MOWERY; OXLEY; SILVERMAN, 1996).

In order to contribute to the AC literature, Camisón & Forés (2010) developed a proposal for multi-dimensional measurement of absorptive capacity. The proposed model consists of two scales with elements that measure Potential and Realized AC. Through a bibliographical review, the authors sought to verify the routines, procedures and activities that integrate potential and actual AC, “as well as the tools with which the measures of the construct are developed, in order to justify the attributes selected to operationalize each dimension of AC” (ROSA; RUFFONI, 2014).

Rosa and Ruffoni (2014) developed an instrument proposal with the aim of structuring different indicators that serve to measure the absorptive capacity of companies that interact with

universities, and the proposal sought to associate AC assessment items in the dimensions of acquisition, assimilation, transformation and exploration. This CA measurement instrument was used in a survey *with* companies that interacted with universities, and the information collected was restructured with a comparative and qualitative method based on *fuzzy sets* .

Hurtado-Ayala and Gonzalez-Campo (2015) present an indicator to measure the degree of knowledge absorption capacity in Colombia. The instrument proposed by the authors has 12 items to mediate AC, the four dimensions suggested by Zahra and George (2002), and was based on a theoretical review of the concept and different types of empirically validated measures. To carry out the estimates, a database created by the Department of National Administration was used, using data from the “Innovation and Technological Development Survey” program (EDIT, by its initials in Spanish) for the manufacturing sector and EDIT for the services in Colombia. The indicator used to measure AC in this model, which varies between 0 and 4, captures the four dimensions of absorption capacity, where 0 implies a zero level of absorption capacity and 4 implies the maximum level of absorption capacity.

The study by authors Guedes, Ziviani, Paiva, Ferreira and Herzog (2017), was adapted from Cohen and Levinthal (1990), and presents the potential and realized dimensions, proposed by Zahra and George (2002), with the respective capabilities: acquisition , assimilation, transformation and exploration of knowledge. The tool used was a questionnaire, applied to 40 solar collector manufacturing companies installed in Brazil, with the aim of evaluating their ability to absorb technology in the manufacture of an innovative product.

The study by Padilha (2020) sought to measure and evaluate the absorptive capacity within the research laboratories of the UFSC-Araranguá campus, also through a questionnaire using the AC dimensions of Zahra and George (2002).

METHODOLOGY

This research has a qualitative approach, and in the first stage, a bibliographical search was carried out on the Capes periodical portal, carrying out a more general search in all databases, filtering articles, dissertations and theses, in Portuguese, English and Spanish, covering the period between 1990 and 2022, using the descriptors "Absorptive Capacity", "Absorptive Capacity", "Absortive Capacity" and "Absorptive Capacity" only in the title of the studies.

In the search for the descriptor "Absorptive Capacity", 232 studies were found, for the descriptor "Absorptive Capacity" 54 studies were found, for the descriptor "Absortive Capacity" 94 were found, and for the descriptor "Absorptive Capacity" 120 studies were found.

According to Prodanov and Freitas (2013, p. 54), through bibliographic research the researcher comes into direct contact with all written production about the content being studied. For the authors, "In bibliographic research, it is important that the researcher checks the veracity of the data obtained, observing possible inconsistencies or contradictions that the works may present" (PRODANOV; FREITAS, 2013, p. 54).

Gil (1999, p. 65) states that the main advantage of bibliographical research is that it allows "[...] the researcher to cover a much wider range of phenomena than that which could be researched directly". This will benefit the researcher's life when they need to face a research problem that highlights certain information and data that are often dispersed or fragmented.

In their studies, Lakatos and Marconi (2003, p. 183) explain that bibliographic research is not characterized as a simple repetition or copy of what has already been written or said on a certain subject, but has the purpose of providing the analysis of a certain topic from another perspective, another aspect or approach.

The importance of bibliographical research is due to the fact that it seeks new discoveries based on knowledge already developed and practiced. It comprises an investigation into subjects similar to the one being investigated, being one of the first stages of the scientific method, helping to avoid the occurrence of duplication of work.

However, in bibliographical research a serious problem may arise: searching only references known to the researcher, or those of his priority, which often results in limiting the literature review. And to solve the problems of bibliographic research and bring more confidence to it, more careful methods were developed, known as the term Systematic Review (MEDEIROS *et al* , 2015).

The second stage of this research will have a theoretical character, using the systematic literature review method, and this methodology is constantly used in the health sector, with the purpose of being comprehensive so that other researchers can replicate it (GALVÃO; PEREIRA, 2014).

Scielo and *Web Of Science* databases , analyzing studies published between the period 1990 and 2022, using the same descriptors mentioned above used to carry out bibliographic research, addressing only research carried out in companies in Latin America.

According to Galvão and Pereira (2014), the systematic literature review “is a type of investigation focused on a well-defined question, which aims to identify, select, evaluate and synthesize the relevant evidence available”.

The systematic review development process encompasses defining each selected study, estimating their quality, identifying significant concepts, comparing the statistical analyzes expressed and concluding about what the literature conveys, also highlighting problems or issues that require new studies (SAMPAIO; MANCINI , 2007).

In this method, a research question is created and then the literature is searched through a selection of articles, dissertations, theses, and information extraction, then the quality of these studies is checked to synthesize them, and Finally, observe and portray the data found.

In table 3 below, the authors Sampaio and Mancini (2007) define the review as being composed of five steps:

Table 3: Systematic Review Steps

Steps	Description
Step 1: Defining the question	The first step to be taken at the beginning of any study is to establish what you want to research. Poorly formulated questions can lead to unclear decisions about what to include in the review later.
Step 2: Searching for the evidence	This step is carried out in indexed electronic databases (based on the selection of uniterms, also known as descriptors constructed with keywords and Boolean operators AND, NOT, OR, etc.).
Step 3: Reviewing and selecting studies	Once we have all the studies to be included, criteria are established to determine their validity and whether there is a possibility that the results may be biased.
Step 4: Analyzing the methodological quality of the studies	Based on similarities between articles, the data will be grouped to obtain final conclusions (or meta-analysis, if this is the case). Each of these groupings should - preferably - be pre-established in advance, avoiding bias.
Step 5: Presenting the results	In the final stages, writing the results must be done taking into account the guiding question established in the first step mentioned above.

Source: adapted from Sampaio and Mancini (2007)

The third and final stage will be a content analysis, being widely disseminated and used, with the aim of analyzing qualitative data. This analysis can be defined as a set of methodological instruments, in continuous improvement, which serves to analyze different sources of content. It is a refined technique, which requires a certain level of intuition, imagination and creativity from the researcher, especially when defining the categories of analysis (FREITAS, CUNHA, & MOSCAROLA, 1997).

Content analysis has three stages: 1) Pre-analysis, which is developed to organize the initial ideas raised by the theoretical framework and propose indicators for understanding the

information collected. 2) Exploration of the material, which consists of building a compilation, taking into account the cutting of texts into recording units, the definition of counting principles and the classification and association of information into representative classes. At this stage, the paragraphs of each interview, the texts of documents, or notes from field diaries are the recording units cut from the collected material. Keywords are identified from these paragraphs, and then each paragraph is summarized to produce a first classification (FOSSÁ, 2003). 3) Interpretation, being the third phase that involves capturing the manifest and potential contents encompassed in all the material collected (interviews, documents and observation). The comparative analysis is carried out through the juxtaposition of the various classes present in each analysis, highlighting the points considered similar and those that are considered different.

According to Fachin (2001), comparative analysis consists of investigating things or situations and interpreting them according to their similarities and differences. It enables the analysis of concrete data and the deduction of similarities and divergences of constant elements, providing observations of an indirect nature.

In this analysis, the comparison will be made by studies that present similar instruments for measuring absorptive capacity within each area of knowledge.

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